
Creation Source of *Unan-unan* Offering Ideas with Computer Embroidery Techniques Using Suede Fabric on the Vest

Silvia Aisyah El Rahma^{1*}, Inty Nahari², Peppy Mayasari³, Marniati⁴

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia¹

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia²

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia³

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia⁴

Corresponding Email: silvia.19038@mhs.unesa.ac.id*

Abstract

Developments in the fashion world continue to experience significant progress, one of which is in the field of fashion. This study aims to formulate the process of creating the source of the idea of offering Unan-unan with a computer embroidery technique using suede fabric on the finished vest, and to find out how the resulting result of the creation of the source of the idea of offering Unan-unan with the computer embroidery technique using suede cloth on the finished vest is relevant based on the Practice-Ied Research method. The result of the creation of the source of the idea of the Unan-unan offering with a computer embroidery technique using suede material in the finished result of this vest is inspired by the head of the buffalo from the traditional ceremony offering of the Unan-unan which is considered the highest position animal by the Tengger people because the buffalo is the largest, strongest, and most helpful animal for humans. The application of the buffalo head as an embroidery motif is a form of appreciation and preservation of the original culture of the tengger tribe, namely the Unan-unan ceremony in the form of a vest.

Keywords: Unan-unan, computer embroidery, vest

Abstrak

Perkembangan dunia fashion terus mengalami kemajuan yang signifikan, salah satunya di bidang fashion. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk merumuskan proses penciptaan sumber ide persembahan Unan-unan dengan teknik bordir komputer menggunakan kain suede pada rompi jadi, dan untuk mengetahui bagaimana hasil penciptaan sumber ide tersebut. penawaran Unan-unan dengan teknik bordir komputer menggunakan kain suede pada rompi jadi relevan berdasarkan metode Penelitian Praktek-Ied. Hasil kreasi sumber ide sesaji Unan-unan dengan teknik bordir komputer menggunakan bahan suede pada hasil akhir rompi ini terinspirasi dari

kepala kerbau dari upacara adat sesaji Unan-unan yang dianggap sebagai hewan dengan kedudukan tertinggi oleh masyarakat Tengger karena kerbau merupakan hewan terbesar, terkuat, dan paling bermanfaat bagi manusia. Penerapan kepala kerbau sebagai motif sulaman merupakan bentuk apresiasi dan pelestarian budaya asli suku tengger yaitu upacara Unan-unan dalam bentuk rompi.

Kata Kunci: Unan-unan, bordir komputer, rompi

Introduction

The Tengger tribe has a variety of cultures ranging from natural conditions, buildings, folklore to regional ceremonies of the Tengger tribe. One of the riches of the Tengger tribe that is very popular and known by local and foreign people and tourists is Mount Bromo (Febriani & Riyanto, 2021). However, not many people know about the traditional ceremonies owned by the Tengger tribe (Sejati et al., 2023). Even today, the Tengger people themselves do not have many participants in the implementation of this traditional ceremony. From the situation of the Tengger tribe, this research was inspired by taking the idea of "*Sesaji Unan-unan*". Unan-unan is one of the major ceremonies for the Tengger community which is held every five years (Febriani & Riyanto, 2021). The unan-unan ceremony aims to purify the village from the interference of spirit creatures and also purify the immature spirit after its physical death (Lelono, 2014). In the implementation of the unan-unan ceremony, an offering containing a buffalo head is required as a symbol of a sacred animal (Sukmawan et al, 2020). From these offerings, this research inspired this research to apply unan-unan offerings into a variety of computer embroidery decorations.

Ornamental variety is an idea in using certain techniques to change the look and feel of a piece of textile material (Marlina & Pertiwi, 2015). In the world of fashion that has unique details, it is very loved by the public. One of them is fashion by using new techniques in its manufacture such as embroidery. At first, embroidery was done manually using hands (Qoriany & Karyaningrum, 2016). Along with the development of technology, embroidery sewing machines were created so that embroidery work became faster. The increasing demand for embroidery has encouraged the development of embroidery machines known as computer embroidery. In accordance with current market developments, embroidery is widely chosen as a fashion support because embroidery can be applied to men's and women's fashion (Magrifah, 2019). The use of embroidery can also be applied to formal and non-formal clothing. Embroidery can also change the appearance of the fabric to look more beautiful. In this study, the embroidery motif used is a buffalo head inspired by the offerings of Unan-unan as a source of ideas.

In its application, embroidery is often applied to cotton, linen, and wool fabrics (Poniecka et al., 2023). The application of embroidery on suede fabric is not widely found on the market. Therefore, in this study, suede fabric was chosen as a material for computer embroidery piling because there are not many studies that apply embroidery to suede materials (Yin & Long, 2023). Suede is a fabric made from animal skin. Suede is usually made from sheepskin, but there are also those made from other types of animals, such as goats, pigs, calves,

and deer. Suede is softer, thinner, and not as strong as traditional full-grain leather (Hermawan, 2019). Suede is a type of fabric that resembles leather but is different, with a finishing process that creates a very smooth and velvety-like layer texture (Ekawati & Yulistiana, 2020). Suede has a wide variety of types. The type of suede chosen in this study is synthetic or imitation suede. Synthetic suede is an alternative because it is more affordable.

Computer embroidery in this study is applied to the finished vest. According to Johnston (2012). The word vest comes from the French *vaitu veste*, from the Italian *vesta* and from the Latin *Vestis*. A vest is a sleeveless garment that covers the upper body (Dai, 2023), usually up to the waist or pelvis. Initially, the vest was designed to provide a neat and structured siluat (Kim, 2011). Vests are usually made of wool, cotton, and polyester fabrics. Vests can be used as formal or casual wear. According to Poespo (2001), a vest for formal events is usually combined with a shirt and suit. Meanwhile, a vest for daily use can provide additional warmth without reducing the user's mobility (Dai, 2023). From this statement, the researcher chose a vest because vests can be used for both formal and non-formal events. The vest can also be an additional lining to warm the body.

Research Method

The creation method used in this study is practice-led research. Practice-led research is a type of scientific work from the results of practical research. According to Hendriyana (2019), practice research has the main characteristic, namely creating and reflecting new works through practical research carried out. Practice-led research methods are included in the category of applied research in the form of works, models, and prototypes.

The flow of the art practice method used in this study is based on the scientific principles of Practice-led Research, in the first stage is the pre-design stage, everything in the first stage provides an overview of the objectives and basic concepts of the research to be carried out. The second stage is stimulation, by realizing visual ideas, then becoming a form of prototype that is built from various aspects of consideration, such as the value, function, and meaning of the work being realized. The third stage is realization, which is the process of visualizing the model in detail by evaluating and conducting feasibility tests on the model/master/prototype that has been made. The fourth stage is presentation. Presentation can be done through exhibitions with the aim of establishing communication, appreciation, and meaning of the works made.

Results and Discussion

The first stage in the creation of the work is exploration. Exploration is a stage of searching and exploring various things including forms, techniques, experimentation potential, and characters that want to appear. The exploration stage is the first step taken by the creator to work on the expected visual form, in this stage the creator tries to hone the ability in terms of imaginative thinking (Gustami, 2007).

In the exploration stage, the first step is field observation and excavation of reference sources and information to determine the theme. In this stage, ideas will be explored in depth, either through articles and journals or interviews with resource persons. After digging up information and ideas, a detailed picture will be produced starting from themes, colors, shapes, to decorations.

Based on the results of interviews with traditional leaders in the Sapikerep area, Probolinggo, at the implementation of the ceremony, several communities such as traditional leaders wore black beskap and black pants. Then it is also equipped with udeng and jarik. The offerings prepared for the ceremony contained 100 skewers, buffalo sacrifices, and several flowers such as kantil flowers, cempaka flowers, and wilted kantiu leaves. From the results of the research study, it was then poured into a mood board.

The next stage is the design of the work. At the design stage of this work, the existing moodboard is poured into a design sketch. Each student made 10 design sketches. From the 10 sketches, 3 designs were selected to be realized. After the shirt sketch was selected, then make several embroidery design sketches from the idea of *sasaji Unan-unan*.

The embroidery designs that have been created based on moodboards resulted in ten alternative designs of the deformation of the shape of the buffalo head. From the four design sketches that have been made, one design to be applied is selected. The selected design is based on the suitability of the design with the theme, namely the offering of *Unan-unan*.

After selecting one design to be realized, it is then necessary to make a working drawing. A working drawing is a visual representation of the design or plan of a construction or manufacturing project. This drawing includes technical details such as dimensions, materials, specifications, and instructions for use necessary to guide the construction or manufacture of a product. Working drawings are typically used by architects, engineers, or craftsmen to understand and realize designs accurately. They can also be used by other related parties, such as contractors, to estimate the costs and resources required. In the construction

process, the working drawings also serve as a guide to ensure that the building or final product is in accordance with the original vision.

Before realizing the design that has been made, the researcher makes a prototype to visualize the product and the concept and design that has been designed. The first prototype made was embroidery. Researchers made two embroidery prototypes, namely machine embroidery and computer embroidery. The results of machine embroidery are quite good and neat, but the manufacturing process takes a long time and the embroidery results are more way than computer embroidery. From the results of the prototype, this research applies the creation

of computer embroidery. The second prototype is a wool vest whose size is adjusted to the selected model.

The next stage is the realization of the work. The realization of a work can mean the process of creating paintings, sculptures, music, or other works of visual art based on initial ideas or inspirations.

No	The Process	Documentation
1	Creating a vest pattern	

2	<p>Preparing tools and materials for making vests</p>	
3	<p>Laying the pattern on the material then cutting the material</p>	
4	<p>The embroidery process, starting from the preparation stage by inputting the design into a worksheet in JPG/BMP format. The second stage is the design that has been moved and then prepared using the <i>Wilcom</i> program by determining the type of stitches and the flow of work. The next stage after adjusting the work flow, from the results of the programming, the embroidery machine will adjust the design to be printed into embroidery which is commonly called the punching process.</p>	
5	<p>Sewing the vest, starting from sewing the shoulders, then sewing the main part and lining, then sewing the sides of the vest, and finally finishing</p>	

6	The result of the vest	
---	------------------------	--

Conclusion

The embroidery design concept in this work focuses on the head of a buffalo which has the meaning of a majestic and sacred animal. The buffalo is a symbol of purification and a form of petition for the Tengger people to be kept away from logs or bad things. The flowers contained in embroidery designs have the meaning of purity and purity. Flowers in offerings reflect sincere and clean intentions.

Soft, less textured fabrics can result in neat, non-wrinkled embroidery while stiff fabrics will produce wrinkled and wavy embroidery. This work applies computer embroidery to a soft but slightly stiff suede fabric, so that the resulting embroidery wrinkles slightly. The creation of computer embroidery with the source of the idea of offering Unan-unan is expected to be a means to introduce the culture of the Tengger tribe, namely the traditional ceremony of *Unan-unan* that is not widely known to the general public.

The results of the process can be in the form of mock ups, prototypes, and mockups. The form of the creation of this work is computer embroidery on the finished vest. Embroidery is located on the back of the vest as the center of interest of the work in this study. The embroidery design is in the form of a buffalo head with flower decorations around it which is inspired by the offerings of *Unan-unan*.

References

- Dai, Y. (2023). Application Research of Computer Artificial Intelligence Technology in Dong Embroidery APP Mini Program. *Proceedings - 2023 International Conference on Computers, Information Processing and Advanced Education, CIPAE 2023*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIPAE60493.2023.00020>
- Ekawati, D. C., & Yulistiana. (2020). Penerapan Teknik Aplikasi Motif Vertisol Pada Busana Pesta Malam. *Journal of Fashion & Textile Design Unesa*.
- Febriani, R., & Riyanto, E. D. (2021). Upacara Adat Tengger di Ambang Komodifikasi: Merawat Tradisi dari Ancaman Desakralisasi. *Jurnal Antropologi: Isu-Isu Sosial Budaya*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.25077/jantro.v23.n2.p148-156.2021>
- Gustami. (2007). *Butir-butir Mutiara Estetika Timur : Ide Dasar Penciptaan Seni Kriya Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: Prasista.
- Hasmia, Riwayani, R., & Rosmiaty. (2021). Analisis Hasil Bordir Komputer Pada Kain Katun, Taffeta, dan Sutra. Universitas Negeri Makassar.

- Hendriyana, H. (2019). *Metodelogi Penelitian Penciptaan Karya*. Yogyakarta: ANDI.
- Hermawan, A. (2019). *Pengembangan Desain Produk Tas Ransel Kulit Dengan Accessories Pelepah Pisang*. Institut Bisnis dan Informatika Stikom Surabaya.
- Johnston, R. (2012). Why Do We Always Leave The Last Button Of A Waistcoat Undone? GQ website: <https://www.gq-magazine.co.uk/article/gq-style-shrink-why-to-leave-the-last-button-of-a-waistcoat-undone>
- Kim, S. Y. (2011). Characteristics of Vest Designs in Contemporary Fashion for Women. *Journal of the Korean Home Economics Association*.
- Lelono, H. (2014). *Upacara Korban Dalam Tradisi Mayu Desa, Tradisi Megalitik Tengger (Studi Etnoarkelogi)*. Balai Arkeologi Yogyakarta.
- Magrifah, S. (2019). *Modifikasi Pakaian Pengantin Pria Minang Dengan Hiasan Bordir Komputer dan Payet*. Padang: Universitas Negeri Padang.
- Marlina, M., & Pertiwi, F. N. (2015). Manfaat Hasil Pelatihan Manipulating Fabric Sebagai Kesiapan Membuka Usaha Aksesoris. *Fesyen Perspektif*.
- Pamungkas, D. T., & Lodra, N. (2018). Tubuh Manusia Sebagai Sumber Ide Pendiptaan Karya Seni Lukis. *Jurnal Seni Rupa*.
- Poespo, G. (2001). Jaket, Mantel, dan Vest. Yogyakarta: 84-91.
- Poniecka, A., Barburski, M., Ranz, D., Cuartero, J., & Miralbes, R. (2023). NEW SOLUTIONS IN THE PRODUCTION OF COMPOSITES - MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH TECHNICAL EMBROIDERY AND WOVEN FABRIC MADE OF FLAX FIBERS. *Vlakna a Textil*, 30(1). <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/008/2023-1-008>
- Qoriany, N. N., & Karyaningrum, A. E. (2016). Pengaruh Perkembangan Bordir Komputer Terhadap Usaha Bordir Manual di Tanggulangin Sidoarjo. *Jurnal Online Tata Busana*.
- Sejati, A. E., Sumarmi, S., Astina, I. K., Susilo, S., & Kurniawati, E. (2023). THE ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION VALUE OF TENGGER TRIBE'S TRADITIONAL CEREMONY IN SUPPORTING THE MOUNT BROMO TOURISM AREA. *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 46(1). <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.46135-1029>
- Sukmawan, S., Setiawati, E., Rizal, M. S., & Febriani, R. (2020). Dimensi Ekologi Folklor Unan-unan Tengger. *Research Gate*.
- Yin, H., & Long, D. (2023). Design of Loading and Unloading Mechanism of Spring Steel Cloth Fixture for Computer Embroidery Machine. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2459(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2459/1/012051>